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AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS IN THE CRITICAL CARE UNIT OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Polypharmacy among critically ill patients significantly elevates the risk of drug-drug interactions (DDIs), which can compromise patient safety and clinical outcomes. Understanding the prevalence and impact of these interactions is crucial for enhancing patient safety, optimizing therapeutic efficacy, and minimizing adverse events. Effective DDI management necessitates diligent monitoring, medication reconciliation, and informed clinical decision-making.

Methods: This study aimed to identify and classify major drug interactions in ICU patients into pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic categories, using Lexicomp software for risk assessment. The number of prescribed medications was recorded, and therapeutic outcomes, observed effects, and severity of interactions were analyzed to determine the potential for clinically significant DDIs.

Results: The study included 93 ICU patients who were prescribed various medications, among which 123 drug interactions were identified. Of these interactions, 15% were classified as major, 69% as moderate, 10% as minor, and 6% as contraindicated. Clopidogrel and heparin were commonly involved as object drugs, while azithromycin and bisoprolol frequently acted as precipitant drugs. Notably, azithromycin and heparin were associated with major interactions. Approximately 28% of interactions had clinically observable effects, with pharmacodynamic interactions being slightly more prevalent. The identified DDIs commonly resulted in adverse outcomes such as toxicity, bleeding, and hypotension. A higher incidence of DDIs was noted in patients over 60 years of age and among female patients.

Conclusion: Drug-drug interactions are prevalent in critically ill patients, particularly among those who are older and experiencing polypharmacy. Regular medication review and vigilant monitoring are imperative to mitigate risks and improve patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Drug-drug interaction refers to a pharmacological or clinical response to the co-administration of two or more drugs that differs from the effects observed when each drug is administered individually. DDIs are distinct from the side effects of individual drugs and can significantly alter therapeutic

outcomes depending on various factors, including the number of drugs taken, duration of therapy, patient age, and disease severity. Patients with chronic illnesses or those undergoing long-term treatments are particularly vulnerable to DDIs due to the frequent need for multiple concurrent

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medications (1). Critically ill patients are especially at risk, as they often receive polypharmacy—the simultaneous use of multiple medications—to manage complex and rapidly changing clinical conditions. Studies estimate that 58–67% of DDIs occur during ICU admissions, largely attributed to the high incidence of infections and the broad spectrum of medications used to manage them (2). Understanding the nature and impact of common DDIs is crucial to prevent adverse outcomes in these high-risk populations.

DDIs are generally categorized into two types:

- Pharmacokinetic interactions, which affect drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, or excretion.
- Pharmacodynamic interactions, which occur at the receptor or physiological system level, leading to additive, synergistic, or antagonistic effects.

The cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzyme system is particularly important in pharmacokinetic interactions. Enzyme induction increases the metabolism of drugs, potentially reducing their efficacy, whereas enzyme inhibition slows drug metabolism, increasing plasma concentrations and the risk of toxicity (3).

In these interactions, precipitant drugs alter the pharmacokinetics or pharmacodynamics of object drugs, often leading to clinically significant consequences. Polypharmacy is a major risk factor for DDIs: the probability of an interaction increases from 6% with two drugs to 50% with five drugs and nearly 100% with ten drugs (1).

The presence of multiple medications and comorbid conditions in critically ill patients necessitates routine screening for potential DDIs. Such interactions can lead to adverse drug reactions, medication errors, reduced treatment adherence, prolonged length of hospital stays, and increased healthcare costs.

They can also result in antagonistic or synergistic effects, which may either compromise therapeutic efficacy or intensify toxicity, especially with drugs that have a narrow therapeutic index (e.g., digoxin, warfarin, phenytoin) (4).

Despite the risks, co-administration of certain drugs is sometimes essential to achieve desired synergistic therapeutic effects. In clinical practice, DDIs are classified by severity into four categories:

- **Contraindicated:** The combination should be avoided due to potentially fatal or serious outcomes.
- **Major:** May cause serious adverse events, hospitalization, or therapeutic failure.
- **Moderate:** Requires medical management but is not immediately life-threatening.
- **Minor:** Usually tolerable and does not require clinical intervention.

Additionally, interaction risk ratings (A, B, C, D, X) help prioritize clinical action:

- **A:** No known interaction
- **B:** No action needed
- **C:** Monitor therapy
- **D:** Consider therapy modification
- **X:** Avoid combination due to high risk (5).

To detect and evaluate DDIs, healthcare providers increasingly rely on digital tools and databases, including Lexicomp, Micromedex, Epocrates, and Medscape. However, discrepancies in classification and severity across platforms necessitate cross-referencing multiple sources for accurate assessment (6).

Hence, this study aims to evaluate drug-drug interactions among patients admitted to the critical care unit of a tertiary care hospital. Secondary objectives include determining the prevalence of major DDIs, classifying them by severity, analyzing risk ratings using Lexicomp, identifying pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic interactions, and

characterizing the object and interacting drugs, along with the observed and theoretical effects.

METHOD

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Critical Care Unit of a tertiary care unit in Bangalore from March 2024 to September 2024. The objective was to assess the prevalence and nature of DDIs among patients admitted to the unit who met the study's inclusion criteria.

Medication charts of the enrolled patients were thoroughly reviewed, and all prescribed medications were evaluated for potential interactions using data collection forms. Drug interactions were identified using Lexicomp drug interaction data base through manual entry and cross verified through Medscape drug interaction application. Interactions were distinguished as Observed and theoretical interactions on the basis of documented clinical effects and toxicity reported along with clinical evidences. Clinically observed drug drug interactions were identified through correlation of observed adverse effects like unexpected bleeding, hypotension, renal impairment with co-administered drug pairs. Some interactions were also assessed through abnormal lab parameters like increase INR, creatinine, electrolyte imbalance also by verification from the databases references from Lexicomp also cross verified with Medscape drug interaction. The causal link was between the drug pair and observed drug outcomes were established based on temporal association and exclusion of alternative etiologies such as underlying disease. Each suspected interaction was scored independently and the causality categorized as definite, probable, possible or doubtful. In addition to medication chart analysis, an extensive medical history was obtained from either the patient or their caregiver.

This included information on current and past medical conditions, ongoing treatments, and any known history of adverse drug reactions. Data supporting potential or observed DDIs were collected and recorded for further analysis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All patients admitted to the Critical Care Unit of the hospital during the study period were considered eligible for inclusion, regardless of gender or underlying disease conditions.

The exclusion criteria were as follows:

- Patients admitted to general wards or other non-critical care units
- Children under the age of 14 years
- Patients admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU)
- Pregnant women
- Immuno-compromised patients
- Patients under OTC medications and herbal supplements

These criteria were strictly adhered to ensure that the sample population accurately reflected the objectives of the study, focusing specifically on drug-drug interactions within the critical care setting.

RESULT

A total of 93 patients were included in the study to evaluate DDIs based on variables such as age, gender, polypharmacy, and other contributing factors. Of these, 55.79% were under the age of 65, while 43.95% were aged 65 years and older. A total of 1,612 medications were prescribed across all patients, with an average of 17.3 drugs per patient. The majority of patients (63.3%) were prescribed between 14 and 21 medications, while 19.36% received 7–13 drugs, and 18.27% were prescribed more than 22 medications.

Higher rates of DDIs were observed among older patients (age >60 years), females, those with longer hospital stays (>5 days), and patients on more than 10 medications. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographics of the subject who underwent the study

Age	N	N%
15 -65 years	52	55.91
More than 65 years	41	44.8
Gender		
Males	45	48.38
Females	48	51.62
Length of stay		
Less than 5 days	6	6.45
5 -30 days	76	81.7
More than 30 days	11	11.8
Number of drugs		
Less than 10	4	3.25
More than 10	119	96.74

A total of 123 drug interactions were identified of which 85(69.1%) were moderate,18(14.64%) were major, 13(10.57%) were minor and 7(5.69%) were contraindicated. In terms of interaction mechanism, 80(65.04%) were pharmacodynamic,40(32.5%)pharmacokinetic, and 3 (2.43%) were unclassified due to unknown mechanism. (Table 2)

Table 2 : Severity and type of drug interactions.

Parameters		No.of interactions (N)	Percentage(N%)
Severity	Major	18	14.6
	Moderate	85	69.1
	Minor	13	10.5
	Contraindicated	7	5.69
		Total	100%
Pharmacodynamic Interaction		80	65.04
Pharmacokinetic Interaction		40	32.5
Unknown mechanism		3	2.43
Total			100%

Major interactions were commonly associated with combinations such as Heparin with Azithromycin and Heparin with Sulfamethoxazole. Frequently involved interacting drugs included Aspirin (13%),Azithromycin(12.19%), Bisoprolol (11.38%), Clopidogrel (11.38%) and Heparin (9.75%) Clopidogrel (11.38%) was the most frequently identified object drug, with Heparin (10.56%) and Aspirin (9.75%) being common precipitant drugs. (Table 3)

Table 3 : Common object drug and precipitant drug involved in the drug interactions.

Object Drug	N (N%)	Precipitant drug	N (N%)
Clopidogrel	14(11.38)	Azithromycin	15(12.19)
Heparin	13(10.56)	Bisoprolol	10(8.13)
Aspirin	12(9.75)	Carbamazepine	5(4.06)
Atorvastatin	8(6.5)	Sodium bicarbonate	5(4.06)
Bisoprolol	7 (5.69)	Quetapine	6(4.87)

Drugs most commonly implicated in interactions belonged to the beta-blocker 28 (11.3%), antiplatelet 22 (8.94%), and anticoagulant 19 (7.7%) classes.

Pharmacodynamic interactions were predominant, occurring in 80 cases (65.85%), with synergistic effects leading to increased toxicity in 35 cases (28.45%), as the most frequently observed clinical outcome. (Table 4 and Table 6)

Out of the 123 potential interactions, only 34 (27.64%) were clinically observed, indicating a discrepancy between predicted and actual DDIs. According to Lexicomp classifications 76 interactions (61.7%) required monitoring (Risk Category C), 30 (24.39%) required therapy modification (D), 11(8.94%) required no action (B), 6(4.87%) were advised to avoid the combination X (Table 5)

The most common management strategy for identified DDIs was to continue therapy with close monitoring, applied in 98 (79.6%) of the identified cases. Dose adjustments were made in 12 (9.75%), drug substitutions in 10(8.13%), and drug discontinuation in 3(2.43%). Notably, no patients were advised to avoid concurrent drug use completely. (Table 7)

Table 4 : Most common major and moderate potential drug interactions.

MAJOR DRUG INTERACTIONS			
OBJECT DRUG	PRECIPITANT DRUG	EFFECT	MANAGEMENT
Heparin	Azithromycin	Bleeding	Monitor INR
Azithromycin	Amiodarone	QT prolongation	Monitor ECG
Diltiazem	Apixaban	Bleeding	Monitor INR
Quetiapine	Olanzapine	QT prolongation	Monitor ECG
MODERATE DRUG INTERACTIONS			
Atorvastatin	Azithromycin	Rhabdomyolysis	Monitor Toxicity
Aspirin	Clopidogrel	Bleeding	Monitor INR
Quetiapine	Bisoprolol	Hypotensive effect	Monitor BP
Lactulose	Sodium bicarbonate	Decrease efficacy	Monitor efficacy

Table 5: Risk rating of drug interaction as per Lexicomp software

Risk rating	N	N (%)
X	6	4.87
B	11	8.94
C	76	61.7
D	30	24.39

Table 6 : Common clinical effects of potential drug drug interactions

CLINICAL EFFECT	N (N%)
Hypotension	10(8.13)
Bleeding	22(17.8)
Decreased efficacy	23(18.69)
Hyperkalaemia	5(4.06)
Increased toxicity	35(28.45)
Bradycardia	03(2.43)
Myopathic effects	2(1.62)
Decreased serum concentration	11(8.94)

Table 7: Management of pDDIs

Management	No.of Patients	Percentage(%)
Avoid concurrent use	0	0
Use of the alternative drug	10	8.13
Discontinuation of drug	3	2.43
Dose adjustment	12	9.75
Continue with monitoring	98	79.6

Theoretical interactions were more frequent 89 (72.35%) than actual observed interactions 34(27.64%), underscoring a significant gap between predicted risk and real-world outcomes. (Table 9)

In summary, the findings indicate that polypharmacy, older age, and female gender are key factors contributing to the prevalence of drug-drug interactions in critically ill patients.

Table 8: Comparison between observed effect and theoretical effect of drug interaction.

Effect	No. of patients	Percentage(%)
Theoretical DIs	89	72.35
Observed DIs	34	27.64

DISCUSSION

Drug-drug interactions refer to the pharmacological or clinical consequences that occur when two or more medications are administered together, affecting each other's mechanism of action. These interactions can lead to unexpected adverse effects, reduced therapeutic efficacy, or increased drug toxicity. DDIs may be classified into pharmacokinetic interactions, which involve changes in absorption, distribution, metabolism, or excretion, and pharmacodynamic interactions, where drug combined action affects the therapeutic outcome.

Despite advancements in medication safety and management protocols, DDIs remain a significant challenge in critical care settings, particularly in tertiary care hospitals where

polypharmacy is highly prevalent. Polypharmacy significantly increases the complexity of treatment regimens, contributing to the rise in clinically significant interactions. In the current study, a high prevalence of polypharmacy was noted, with most patients receiving multiple medications, thereby increasing the likelihood of potential DDIs.

This study analysed 93 patients to assess the influence of various factors such as age, gender, length of hospital stay, number of prescribed medications, and the severity and clinical effects of drug interactions. The mean age of the study population was 62 years, with a female predominance, consistent with findings from Uijtendaal et al (7). Still, it was in contrast to the study conducted by Bhavika Ravindra Wagh, showing predominance of males (61.75%) (8).

Approximately 15% of identified DDIs were classified as major, although a higher rate was reported in a similar study conducted by Sarah Mahmoud Abd El Samia Mohamed et al. in Egypt (11). The majority of interactions in this study were of moderate severity, necessitating regular monitoring, findings that align with the studies by Uijtendaal et al. (9), and Hammes J¹², whereas the majority of interactions were of major severity in the similar study conducted by Bhavika Ravindra Wagh (14).

Among the top five potential DDIs identified, the interaction between Clopidogrel and Aspirin ranked highest, corroborating findings from Mohamed et al. (10) and Bertolia et al. (13). According to Lexicomp's risk rating, Type C interactions, which require close monitoring, were most common, accounting for 61.7% of cases. This is consistent with studies conducted by Yetskinyogun et al. and Haji Aghajani et al. (12). The class of drugs commonly contributing in DDIs included beta-blockers, antiplatelets, anticoagulants, and anticonvulsants.

These findings were contrast with the study conducted by Sainul Abideen et al. (11), who reported anticonvulsants as the second most frequent drug class implicated in interactions. The most frequent clinical consequences observed were increased toxicity (28.45%), decreased efficacy (18.69%), and bleeding (17.8%), consistent with findings from Uijtendaal et al.(9). Other observed effects included hypotension, hypoglycemia, and bradycardia.

In terms of interaction type, pharmacodynamic interactions predominated (66%), slightly outnumbering pharmacokinetic interactions, a distribution that aligns with the study by Adriano Max Moreira Reis et al. (5), which highlighted the prominence of metabolic mechanisms among pharmacokinetic DDIs.

A comparison of predicted (theoretical) versus clinically observed drug interactions revealed that only 27.64% of identified potential DDIs resulted in observable clinical effects. Among the drugs most frequently implicated, Clopidogrel (11.38%) emerged as the most common object drug, followed by Heparin (10.56%). As for precipitant drugs, Azithromycin (12.19%) and Bisoprolol (8.13%) were the most commonly involved, findings that are consistent with those reported by Uijtendaal et al. (9).

Overall, the study underscores the importance of vigilant medication monitoring, especially in older patients and those undergoing complex treatment regimens involving multiple drugs. The gap between potential and observed DDIs also suggests a need for improved clinical decision-support systems and ongoing risk-benefit evaluation of concurrent therapies in critical care.

CONCLUSION

This study identified 123 potential drug-drug interactions among 93 patients, with 18 (15%) classified as major and the majority being of moderate severity, emphasizing the need for vigilant medication monitoring. Most interactions were pharmacodynamic, commonly involving beta-blockers, antiplatelets, and anticonvulsants. The most frequent major interaction was between heparin and azithromycin, while aspirin and clopidogrel accounted for the most common moderate interaction. Clinically, 34(27.64%) of the interactions were observed, with increased drug toxicity being the most prevalent adverse outcome. These findings highlight the importance of active involvement by trained pharmacists, routine medication reconciliation, adverse effect monitoring, and regular medication reviews particularly in under-reported tertiary care settings. Moving forward, integrating advanced drug interaction alert systems into Health Enhanced Electronic Records (EHR) can offer real-time, evidence-based guidance to healthcare providers, ultimately improving patient safety and enhancing treatment outcomes.

LIMITATIONS

The research was conducted at a single tertiary care center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings or more diverse patient populations. The limited duration of the study restricted the ability to assess long-term outcomes and identify delayed adverse drug interactions. Data accuracy have been compromised due to incomplete or inaccurate patient histories, as some patients or caregivers may have unintentionally omitted clinically relevant information.

Conducting the study in critical care units posed challenges to patient participation and communication, potentially leading to gaps in data collection. This study had limited scope mainly the detection and classification of potential drug drug interactions and the study design was descriptive and non-interventional it did not include any active interventions, cost analysis or preventive strategies to reduce drug interaction risk is one of the limitation of the study. The short timeframe of data collection may have prevented the observation of seasonal trends or variations in prescribing patterns, thereby limiting the depth of the analysis.

SUMMARY

123 DDIs were found among 93 ICU patients; 15% were significant, 69% were moderate, 10% were mild, and 6% were contraindicated. Azithromycin and bisoprolol were popular precipitants, whereas heparin and clopidogrel were common object drugs. Heparin and azithromycin had significant interactions. Approximately 28% experienced significant side effects, mostly pharmacodynamic ones that resulted in hypotension and toxicity. DDIs were more common in female patients and those over 60. Particularly in under reported tertiary care settings, our data highlight the importance of pharmacist involvement, routine drug reviews, and adverse effect monitoring. Advanced DDIs alert systems can optimise results, increase patient safety, and facilitate real-time decision-making when integrated into electronic health records. In summary, the findings indicate that polypharmacy, older age, and female gender are key factors contributing to the prevalence of drug-drug interactions in critically ill patients.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study. The research was conducted independently, and the findings represent the unbiased results and interpretations of the authors.

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Data Availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The data will be made available to qualified researchers for non-commercial purposes only, subject to ethical and privacy considerations. Due to privacy restrictions, participant data cannot be publicly shared, but can be accessed by contacting the corresponding author.

Protection of humans and animals.

The authors declare that no experiments involving humans or animals were conducted for this research.

Confidentiality, informed consent, and ethical approval

The authors have followed their institution's confidentiality protocols, obtained informed consent from patients, and received approval from the Ethics Committee. The SAGER guidelines were followed according to the nature of the study.

Declaration on the use of artificial intelligence.

The authors declare that no generative artificial intelligence was used in the writing of this manuscript

Author's contribution:

- Dr Merit Koju- responsible for conducting literature review and supervising the overall study, including data collection, manuscript formatting, submissions and handling the revisions.
- Dr Sachin A H- conducted the literature review and initial drafting of the manuscript and maintained the collected data for analysis.
- Dr Jeeva George – served as a guide, Assistant professor, department of pharmacy practice contributed during several preliminary versions of the study text and helped in making critical suggestions and posing challenging questions
- Dr Balakeshwa Ramaiah - served as a co-guide and HOD of Pharmacy Practice and contributed with expertise in methodology and editing the final manuscript.
- All the authors equally contributed to the reviewing and approval of the final manuscript.

Abbreviations

- DDIs: Drug drug interactions
- EHR: Health Enhanced Electronic Records
- NICU: Neonatal intensive care unit
- CYP: cytochrome